

Bridgehead Nitrogen Heterocycles : Synthesis and Biological Activities of *s*-Triazolo[3,4-*b*][1,3,4]thiadiazole System

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Manuscript received 27 September 1994, revised 10 March 1995, accepted 15 March 1995

In continuation of our work in the chemistry of heterocycles¹, we thought it of interest to synthesise a triazolothiadiazole system which may be viewed as a cyclic analogue of two very important components, i.e. thiosemicarbazide² and biguanide³ which often display diverse biological activities. The starting compounds 4-amino-3-substituted-phenyl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles (**1**) were synthesised via carboxylic acid hydrazide⁴ according to the reported procedure⁵. Compound **1** showed ir bands at 3 240, 3 150 (NH₂) and 1 130 cm⁻¹ (SH) and ¹H nmr signals at δ 5.6 (2H, s, NH₂) and 13.5 (1H, s, SH).

Condensation of **1** with 2,4-dialkoxy-5-alkylbenzaldehydes (**2**) in presence of *p*-toluenesulphonic acid⁶ gave 3-aryl-6-[(2,4-dialkoxy-5-alkyl)phenyl]-5,6-dihydro-*s*-triazolo[3,4-*b*][1,3,4]thiadiazoles (**3a-p**; Table 1) and revealed ir bands at 1 600 (C=N) and 3 000–3 250 cm⁻¹ (NH) and ¹H nmr signals at δ 6.0–6.4 (1H, bs, NH, exchangeable with D₂O) and 6.8–7.4 (m, ArH).

μg ml⁻¹ in the nutrient agar media. The compounds were not significantly active towards these bacteria. The antifungal screening was carried out *in vitro* by paper-disc method⁷ against two fungi, viz. *Aspergillus niger* and *Candida albicans*, and did not exhibit significant activity.

All the compounds were tested for antiinflammatory activity by acute carrageenan edema test model in rats⁸. Compounds **3f** (52.95% inhibition), **3i** (53.68%), **3n** (54.00%) and **3p** (53.50%) were found to possess significant activity while others showed mild to moderate activity (16.08–44.67%).

Experimental

M.ps. were taken on a Buchi apparatus and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu IR-435 spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a Varian T60-A instrument (60 MHz) using Me₄Si as the internal standard. All the compounds were checked for their purity on tlc plates.

TABLE I—M P DATA OF COMOPUNDS **3a-p***

Compd no	R	R ¹	R ²	R ³	Mp °C
3a	C ₆ H ₅	C ₂ H ₅	CH ₃	CH ₃	118–5
b	C ₆ H ₅	C ₂ H ₅	C ₂ H ₅	C ₂ H ₅	101–03
c	C ₆ H ₅	C ₂ H ₅	C ₂ H ₅	CH ₃	142–44
d	C ₆ H ₅	C ₂ H ₅	CH ₃	C ₂ H ₅	112–13
e	C ₆ H ₅	C ₃ H ₇	CH ₃	CH ₃	119–20
f	C ₆ H ₅	C ₃ H ₇	C ₂ H ₅	C ₂ H ₅	136–38
g	C ₆ H ₅	C ₃ H ₇	C ₂ H ₅	CH ₃	114–16
h	C ₆ H ₅	C ₃ H ₇	CH ₃	C ₂ H ₅	90–91
i	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂	C ₂ H ₅	CH ₃	CH ₃	110
j	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂	C ₂ H ₅	C ₂ H ₅	C ₂ H ₅	143
k	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂	C ₂ H ₅	C ₂ H ₅	CH ₃	137–6
l	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂	C ₂ H ₅	CH ₃	C ₂ H ₅	116–17
m	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂	C ₃ H ₇	CH ₃	CH ₃	99–4
n	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂	C ₃ H ₇	C ₂ H ₅	C ₂ H ₅	134–35
o	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂	C ₃ H ₇	C ₂ H ₅	CH ₃	96–97
p	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂	C ₃ H ₇	CH ₃	C ₂ H ₅	115–16

*All the compounds showed satisfactory C, H and N analyses

Biological activities : The antimicrobial activity of **3a-p** was determined *in vitro* with paper-disc method⁷ against *Eschericia coli* (Gram-negative) and *Staphylococcus aureus* (Gram-positive) at concentrations 1000, 100 and 10

3-Aryl-6-[(2,4-dialkoxy-5-alkyl)phenyl]-5,6-dihydro-*s*-triazolo[3,4-*b*][1,3,4]thiadiazoles (**3a-p**). **General procedure** : An equimolar mixture of **1** (0.01 mol), aldehyde **2** (0.01 mol) and *p*-toluenesulphonic acid (20 mg) in diethylbenzene (100 ml) was refluxed for 10 h using Dean-Stark apparatus. The mixture was then cooled and treated with water (100 ml). The organic layer thus separated was washed with water (2 × 50 ml) and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Benzene was then evaporated under reduced pressure and the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol, (54–75%).

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (S.S.) is thankful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for the award of a Senior Research Fellowship.

References

1. R. GUPTA, S. PAUL, M. SHARMA, S. SUDAN, P. SOMAL and P. L. KACHROO, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1993, **32**, 1187.
2. K. C. JOSHI and S. GIRI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **40**, 42; M. C. GOLDSWORTHY, *Phytopathol.*, 1942, **32**, 498.
3. J. HAGLIND, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1966, **64**, 16509.
4. S. KAKIMOTO, I. SEKIKAWA and J. NISHIE, *J. Chem. Soc. Jpn., Pure Chem. Sect.*, 1953, **74**, 6 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1954, **48**, 120719).
5. J. R. REID and N. D. HEINDEL, *J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1976, **13**, 925.
6. J. B. BICKING, M. G. BOOK, E. J. CRAGOE, R. M. DIPARDO, N. P. GOULD, W. J. HOLTZ, T. J. LEE, C. M. ROBB, R. L. SMITH, J. P. SPRINGER and E. H. BLAINE, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1983, **26**, 342; H. K. GAKHAR, A. JAIN and S. B. GUPTA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, **59**, 900.
7. G. CZERKINSKY, N. DIDING and P. OUCHTERLENG, *Scand. J. Clin. Lab. Invest.*, 1955, **7**, 259.
8. C. A. WINTER, E. A. RISLEY and G. W. NUSS, *Proc. Soc. Exp. Biol. Med.*, 1962, **111**, 544.